

CHALLENGES IN LEARNING SCIENCES AMONG SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL SCIENCE, TECHNOLOGY, ENGINEERING, AND MATHEMATICS (STEM) STUDENTS OF PRIVATE SCHOOL IN INDANAN, SULU

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ABSTRACT

Science education is one of the most crucial subjects among Senior high School students especially in the Science Technology Engineering and Mathematics Strand (STEM). This study aimed to explore the challenges of learning science among senior high school STEM students of SCT Inc. and to determine the factors in learning sciences. Data were collected through a survey questionnaire. Frequency count and percentage were used to determine the demographic profile of the respondents and mean and standard deviation were used to determine the extent of challenges in learning Sciences in terms of teacher factors, subject matter, student ability, parental support, T-tests for gender, and (ANOVA) for other profile were used to determine the significant difference, and correlational analysis to determine the significant correlation between the extent of the challenges in learning Sciences in terms of teacher factors, subject matter, student ability, and parental support. It was found that more than half of the respondents are between 18 – and 19 years old, 140 are females, more than half earn P5,000.00 and below monthly, and less than half of their parents reached the elementary level, no significant difference was found when data are grouped according to other profiles except in terms of age, and moderate relationship was found between the teacher factors and subject matter and low correlation between student ability and parental support. By analyzing the challenges of STEM students and educators can refine their teaching methodology, incorporate more effective instructional techniques, and create a more engaging and supportive learning environment.

Keywords: *Challenges, Science, STEM Students, Sulu College of Technology Inc.*

INTRODUCTION

Science nowadays has become prevalent in our society, it became revolutionized in the community which made a high standard of education significant for both students and teachers as well, revolutionized in a sense that it is indeed continuous as uttered by Sabbaha N. et. al, (2024) Learning is the soul of education that eliminates ignorance within individual's mind, it is an ability possessed by human being that plays a crucial role in the existence of human life, from the moment a person was brought into this world, the process of learning begins until he or she reaches the stage of late adulthood which means that learning is a continuous process. It utilizes humanism which involves the holistic you, focusing the mental, emotional, and moral development. Many ways of studies like analyzing, assessing, applying, giving hypotheses, and most especially giving an evaluation to any problem concern and proven data.

All educational programs, from basic to higher, have included science instruction. The scientific curriculum makes a distinction between how science and technology are used in day-to-day human endeavors. A. Hasni & P. Potvin (2015) stated in school, students have an interest in studying science especially if it is emphasized clearly, logically, and comprehensively. Science and technology inhabit a dominant position in the growth and progress of the nation. It helps in developing progress that leads to the advancement and success of a country. Despite the positive feedback of studying science education, it has been observed that learners are fearful of studying the subject. This implies the negative attitude and poor performance of the learners in learning science and technology.

In today's 21st century, students are facing multiple problems in the field of science education. Explanations based on science and technology will likely offer corrective measures to some of these difficulties. Yet, as we recognize today, science and technology are inaccessible to a vast human population. Some of society's persistent problems today are linked to the depletion of natural resources, growing poverty, hunger, and illiteracy in many nations worldwide.

Kaptan & Timurlenk (2012) stated that some of the pressing challenges in learning science are an insufficient number of science teachers, lack of motivation among learners and low self-assurance in learning science, huge numbers of students in every class, broken connection with other lessons, inadequate number of laboratory equipment and facilities, insufficient time distribution for science education despite the intensive curriculum. With the inception of Education 4.0, students are likewise expected to be digitally literate to learn science better.

In the Philippines, most of the students are facing several challenges, examples are family problems, poverty, the large number of students in each classroom, lack of

motivation and low self-confidence, difficulty in science, and bullying. Each of these problems has a great impact on the student's learning process.

John Rae & Rianna Yvette (2020), The absence of resources and infrastructure for science education presented several issues. There are further difficulties with the language of instruction, the learners' backgrounds, and the absence of parental support. These difficulties have a detrimental impact on learning and should be immediately addressed.

Jailani, A. et.al, (2024) Although the pandemic may have passed by now, its effects are still felt, thus education needs to continue. We all think that education is the key to success, thus it shouldn't be interrupted, so the government has come up with a way to meet the demands of the kids while allowing the children to continue their education. Since student learning is one of the government's top concerns, the concept of continuous education has been under fire.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

This paper sought to investigate the extent of challenges in learning sciences among Senior High School STEM students of Sulu College of Technology Inc., this study aims to answer the following question:

1. What is the demographic profile of Senior High School STEM students of Sulu College of Technology Inc. in terms of;
 - 1.1 Age;
 - 1.2 Gender;
 - 1.3 Parents' Average Monthly Income; and,
 - 1.4 Parent's Educational Attainment?

2. What is the extent of the challenges encountered in learning Sciences among Senior High School STEM Students of Sulu College of Technology Inc. to;
 - 2.1 Teacher Factors;
 - 2.2 Subject Matter;
 - 2.3 Student Ability; and
 - 2.4 Parental Support?

3. Is there a significant difference in the challenges encountered in learning Sciences among Senior High School STEM Students of Sulu College of Technology Inc. when data are grouped according to age, gender, parents' average monthly income, and parents' educational attainment?

4. Is there any significant correlation among the sub-categories subsumed under challenges in learning Science among senior high school STEM students of Sulu College of Technology Inc. as to Teacher Factors, Subject Matter, Student Ability, and Parental Support?

METHODOLOGY

Locale of the study

This study was conducted in one of the Private schools in the Municipality Indanan province of Sulu. Chinese School formerly known as Tonjing, and founded by Engr. Sambas I. Hassan Al-Haj, SULU COLLEGE OF TECHNOLOGY INC. during the school year 2021-2022, To find out the challenges in learning science among Senior high school in the said school.

Research Design

The study used a correlational research design with survey questionnaires as the main instrument for gathering the required data. The present study surveyed the challenges in learning science among senior high school STEM students of Sulu College of Technology Inc. Research is concerned with relationships between variables without the research controlling or manipulating any of them and reflects the strength and/or direction of the relationship between two or more variables which prevail in group cases chosen for the study using quantitative approaches.

Correlational research is a type of non-experimental research method in which a researcher measures two or more variables, the correlational study looks for variables that seem to interact with each other when you say one variable changes you have a fair idea of how other variables will change. This method is very appropriate because the study involved understanding and assessing the statistical relationship between the variables of the challenges in learning science by senior high school Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) students. The questionnaire is the main instrument used to gather data needed in the study.

Sampling Design

The sampling technique used in this particular study was purposive sampling, which means that the researcher purposively chose all the senior high school Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) students of Sulu College of Technology Inc. Two hundred (200) students were optimized as subjects.

Research Instrument

To answer the specific problems in this research, the instrument adopted from the study of John Rae (2020) will be used to achieve the aim of the study but some applicable changes are made to shape the present study. It consists of two (2) parts. Part I seeks information about the respondent's sex, gender, parents' average monthly income, and educational attainment. The next part is the respondents' problems in learning science, which includes teacher factors, Subject Matter, Student Ability, and Parental Support. The

respondent will choose from Strongly Agree, Agree, Fair, Disagree, and Strongly Disagree check one answer on the corresponding box that describes their response.

Statistical Treatment of Data

A descriptive statistical tool was appropriately employed in the treatment of data to be gathered for this study, namely:

1. For research number one (1) Frequency counts and percentages will be employed to determine the profile of Senior High School STEM Students.

2. For research number two (2) Mean and standard deviation will be employed to determine the extent of challenges encountered in learning science among senior high school STEM students of Sulu College of Technology Inc. during the School Year 2021-2022.

3. For research problem number three (3) T-tests for independent samples will be employed to determine the significant differences in the extent of Challenges encountered in learning science among senior high school STEM students of Sulu College of Technology Inc. when they are grouped according to gender. One-way Analysis of variance (ANOVA) will be employed to determine the significant differences when they are grouped according to age, parents' average monthly income, and parents' educational attainment.

4. For research problem number four (4) Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (Pearson's r) will be employed to determine the degree of correlation among the sub-categories subsumed under the extent of Challenges encountered in learning science among senior high school STEM students of Sulu College of Technology Inc.

Scope and Delimitation

This study focuses on challenges in learning sciences among senior high school STEM students in Sulu College of Technology Inc. The respondent of this study is delimited to the Science Technology Engineering and Mathematics students of Sulu College of Technology Inc. during the school year 2022-2023.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. *What is the demographic profile of the Senior High School STEM students of Sulu College of Technology Inc. in terms of 1.1 age, 1.2 gender, 1.3 parents' average monthly income, and 1.4 parent's educational attainment?*

Table 1.1 Demographic Profile in terms of Age

Age	Number of Respondents	Percentage
16 – 17 years old	64	32%
18 – 19 years old	104	52%
20 years old and above	32	16%
TOTAL	200	100%

1.1 Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Age

Table 1.1 shows the demographic profile in terms of age. It showed that 32% of the respondent are between 16-17 years of age, 52% are between 18 – 19 years old, and only 16% are 20 years old and above.

Table 1.2 Demographic Profile in terms of Gender

Gender	Number of Respondents	Percentage
Male	50	25%
Female	150	75%
TOTAL	200	100%

1.2 Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Gender

Table 1.2 presents the demographic profile in terms of gender. It showed that 75% of the respondents are females and only 25% are males.

Table 1.3 Demographic Profile in terms of Parents' Average Monthly Income

Parents' Average Monthly Income	Number of Respondents	Percentage
P5,000.00 and below	130	65%
P5,001.00 – 10,000.00	46	23%
P10,001 – 15,000.00	16	8%
P15,001 and above	8	4%
TOTAL	200	100%

1.3 Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Parents' Average Monthly Income

Table 1.3 presents the demographic profile of the respondent in terms of the parent's average monthly income. It showed that 65% of the parents earn P5,000.00 and below monthly and only 4% earn P15,001.00 and above monthly.

Table 1.4 Demographic Profile in terms of Parent's Education Attainment

Parent's Educational Attainment	Number of Respondents	Percentage
Elementary Level	74	37%
High School Level	44	22%
College Level	54	27%
Post Graduate	28	14%
TOTAL	200	100%

1.4 Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Parent's Educational Attainment

Table 1.4 presents the parent's educational attainment. It showed that 37% of the parents are elementary level and only 14% reached postgraduate in education.

2. What is the extent of the challenges encountered in learning Sciences among Senior High School STEM students of Sulu College of Technology Inc. as to; teacher factors, subject matter, student ability, and parental support?

Table 2.1 Extent of the Challenges Encountered in Learning Sciences among Senior High School STEM Students of Sulu College of Technology Inc. as to Teacher Factors

Statements	Mean	Interpretation
1. My Teacher does not have a proficient mastery of science concepts.	1.63	Disagree
2. My Teacher does not use creative and intriguing methods of teaching.	1.62	Disagree
3. My Teacher does not instruct science effectively.	1.73	Disagree
4. My Teacher does not ignite my curiosity in my scientific lessons.	1.89	Disagree
5. My science teacher did not have enough preparation before going to class.	2.22	Disagree
6. The teacher's method of teaching Science, does not Improve my academic performance.	2.32	Disagree
7. My Science Teacher has made me feel anxious.	2.28	Disagree
8. Teachers do not allow students to use other references on Science Subjects.	2.55	Fair
9. The teaching techniques of my teacher are more learner-centered.	2.39	Disagree
10. Teachers are more dependent on ICT.	2.30	Disagree
Average	2.10	Disagree

LEGEND 5(Strongly Agree) 4.50 – 5.00 4(Agree) 3.50 – 4.49 3(Fair) 2.50 – 3.49 2(Disagree)1.50 – 2.49 Disagree 1(Strongly Disagree)1.00 – 1.49

In **Table 2.1** on the extent of challenges encountered in terms of teacher factors, the result showed that the respondents **disagreed** on nine (9) of the statements and some of these are; teaching techniques of the teacher are more learner-centered (mean = 2.39) and the teachers are more dependent on ICT (mean = 2.30). One (1) of the statement showed **fair**. The average mean of 2.10 which means the respondents **disagree** on the extent of the challenges encountered in terms of teacher factors.

The result implies that the respondents do not agree that the challenges they encountered in learning Sciences have something to do with the teacher factors.

Black & Wiliam (1998) Interaction between teachers and students is essential for teaching to be effective in generating learning. For most students, a teacher's one-way instruction is ineffective. A crucial component of this engagement is assessment for learning, which is a refined version of formative assessment. A thorough analysis of the Research has demonstrated that there is strong evidence that formative evaluation raises students' attainment as determined by summative assessment, resulting in notable gains in test scores. This kind of assessment has always been discouraged, especially for science teachers.

According to Abdurahman (2024) instructor at MBHTE-Sulu majority (50%) are between the ages of 36 and 45; in terms of their educational background eligibility, 110 people (61.1%) have completed their bachelor's degree. Furthermore, the majority (44.4%) of those with teaching experience have worked for five to ten years which is why the teachers are qualified to teach and the students do not agree that the challenges they encountered in learning sciences have something to do with teacher factors.

Table 2.2 Extent of the Challenges Encountered in Learning Sciences among Senior High School STEM Students of Sulu College of Technology Inc. as to Subject Matter

Statements	Mean	Interpretation
1. Properties and structure of matter are complex.	2.55	Fair
2. The parts and functions of animals and plant cells are difficult to understand.	2.71	Fair
3. Topics about heredity are unclear to me.	2.74	Fair
4. Biodiversity and evolution involve complex topics.	2.66	Fair
5. The symbiotic relationship in the ecosystem is hard to understand.	2.42	Disagree
6. The processes of learning about energy are complex.	2.71	Fair
7. The processes of calculating force and motion are complicated.	2.54	Fair
8. Concepts in geology are not simplified.	2.15	Disagree

9. Topics in meteorology are confusing.	2.23	Disagree
10. Concepts in astronomy are unclear.	2.34	Disagree
Average	2.51	Fair

LEGEND 5(Strongly Agree) 4.50 – 5.00 4(Agree) 3.50 – 4.49 3(Fair) 2.50 – 3.49
2(Disagree)1.50 – 2.49 Disagree 1(Strongly Disagree)1.00 – 1.49

In **Table 2.2** on the extent of the challenges encountered in terms of subject matter, the result showed that the respondents indicated fair on 6 statements and disagreed on the rest of the statements. Among those they indicated **fair** are; topics about heredity are unclear to them (mean = 2.74) and the parts and functions of animals and plant cells are difficult to understand (mean = 2.71). Among those they **disagreed** are; that the symbiotic relationship in the ecosystem is hard to understand (mean = 2.42) and concepts in Astronomy are unclear (mean = 2.34,). The average mean of 2.51 is interpreted as **fair** on the challenges encountered in learning Sciences in terms of subject matter.

It implies that the subject matter in sciences is somehow challenging to the Senior High School STEM students of Sulu College of Technology Inc.

According to Tan & Kim (2020), The rapid growth of science and technology has brought to light societal and cultural norms and values, as well as changes in the environment and climate. These factors have a tremendous influence on children and youth's lives and, consequently, on how they learn.

Table 2.3 Extent of the Challenges Encountered in Learning Sciences among Senior High School STEM Students of Sulu College of Technology Inc. as to Student Ability

Statements	Mean	Interpretation
1. I face difficulty in analyzing experiments even when there is an example given.	2.49	Disagree
2. I do not perform well in science.	2.38	Disagree
3. Science is more difficult for me than for many of my classmates.	2.45	Disagree
4. I do not learn things quickly in science.	2.47	Disagree
5. I have a poor conceptual and procedural understanding of science.	2.40	Disagree
6. I have poor reading comprehension skills in science activities.	2.39	Disagree
7. Poor study habits in science subjects affect my Academic performance.	2.66	Fair
8. I have poor analytical thinking in science.	2.44	Disagree
9. Lack of experience in Experimenting.	2.34	Disagree
10. Have an insufficient background in science in the lower grades.	2.38	Disagree

Average	2.44	Disagree
LEGEND 5(Strongly Agree) 4.50 – 5.00	4(Agree) 3.50 – 4.49	3(Fair) 2.50 – 3.49
2(Disagree) 1.50 – 2.49	Disagree 1(Strongly Disagree) 1.00 – 1.49	

In **Table 2.3** on the extent of the challenges encountered in terms of student ability, the respondents indicated **fair** in only one statement and that is that poor study habits in science subjects affect their academic performance (mean = 2.66). Nevertheless, they indicated **disagree** with the other 9 statements, and among these are; that they face difficulty in analyzing experiments even when there is an example given (mean =2.49), they do not learn things quickly in science (mean = 2.47), and Science is more difficult for them than many of their classmates (mean = 2.44,). The average mean of 2.44 is interpreted as **disagree** with the challenges encountered in learning Sciences among STEM students of SCT Inc.

The result simply implies that student ability is not a problem as far as challenges encountered in learning Sciences among Senior High School STEM students of SCT Inc.

Similarly, to the study by John Rae & Rianna Yvette (2020), Students often don't face many difficulties in studying science from all angles using the quantitative outcomes of the research.

Table 2.4 Extent of the Challenges Encountered in Learning Sciences among Senior High School STEM Students of Sulu College of Technology Inc. as to Parental Support

Statements	Mean	Interpretation
1. My Parents cannot support my financial needs in science.	1.70	Disagree
2. My parents cannot assist me with my science project.	1.67	Disagree
3. My parents cannot support me with my studies in the science subject.	1.71	Disagree
4. My parents do not have an interest in guiding me in my experimental activities in the science subject.	1.85	Disagree
5. My Parents/Guardians do not attend our science-related programs and school activities.	2.04	Disagree
6. My Parents/Guardians do not encourage me to take Science at all levels.	2.02	Disagree
7. My Parents/Guardians are not concerned with my science output.	1.98	Disagree
8. My Parents/guardians are not used to monitoring my results formatively.	2.20	Disagree
9. My Parents/Guardians do not have contact with my science teacher to ask for my skills in the subject.	2.20	Disagree

10. My Parents/Guardians are not open-minded about this subject. 1.94 Disagree

Average 1.93 Disagree

LEGEND 5(Strongly Agree) 4.50 – 5.00 4(Agree) 3.50 – 4.49 3(Fair) 2.50 – 3.49
2(Disagree)1.50 – 2.49 Disagree 1(Strongly Disagree)1.00 – 1.49

Table 2.4 on the challenges in learning Sciences in terms of parental support. The respondents indicated **disagree** with 01256 all statements and some of these are; their parents/guardians do not attend their Science – related programs and school activities (mean = 2.40), their parents/guardians are not used to monitor their formative results (mean = 2.20), their parents/guardians do not have contact with them

Science teacher to ask for their skills in the subject (mean = 2.20, SD = .891). The average mean of 1.93 is interpreted as **disagree** on the extent of the challenges in learning Sciences among the Senior High School STEM students of SCT Inc.

The result simply implies that parental support does not add to the extent of the challenges in learning Sciences among the Senior High School STEM students of SCT Inc.

According to Evans (2006), Parenting programs are designed to improve or alter parents' attitudes, beliefs, and behaviors related to raising a child, as well as to raise awareness of the critical role parents play in fostering their children's growth and development.

3. Is there a significant difference in the extent of the challenges encountered in learning Sciences among Senior High School STEM students of Sulu College of Technology Inc. when data are classified according to age, gender, parent's average monthly income, and parent's educational attainment?

The t-test was used for gender since there are only two categories. The value of $t = 43.174$ is greater than the $p = .05$, 2-tailed tests. It means that the null hypothesis is accepted.

There is no significant difference in the extent of the challenges encountered in learning Sciences among Senior High School STEM students of Sulu College of Technology Inc. when data are classified and grouped according to their gender.

Table 3.1 t-test for Significant Difference in terms of Gender

	T	Df	Sig.(2-tailed)	Mean difference	95% confidence interval of the difference	
					Lower	Upper
Gender	43.174	93	.000	1.798	1.72	1.88

Significant at .05 level

In **Table 3.2** Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) for age, parent's average monthly income, and parent's educational attainment was used. The f value of .008 for age is lesser than the sig. value of .05, the f value of 2.813 for the parent's average monthly income is greater than the sig. value of .05, and the f value of 1.253 for the parent's educational attainment is also greater than the sig value of .05. It could only mean that the null hypothesis is rejected in terms of age and accepted in terms of the parent's average monthly income and parent's educational attainment.

There is no significant difference in the extent of the challenges encountered in learning Sciences among Senior High School STEM students of Sulu College of Technology Inc. when data are classified according to parents' average monthly income and parents' educational attainment. However, there is a significant difference in terms of age. The result implies that the age of the respondents has something to do with the challenges encountered by the Senior High School STEM students of SCT Inc. in learning Sciences while parent's average monthly income and parent's educational attainment do not contribute to the challenges encountered by them.

The result supports that **Constructivist education** is predicated on the idea that rather than just having students absorb information, learning happens when students actively participate in the process of creating meaning and knowledge. The creators of meaning and knowledge are the learners. Constructivist education produces motivated, autonomous students and encourages critical thinking.

Table 3.2 ANOVA for Significant Difference in terms of Age, Parent's Average Monthly Income, and Parent's Educational Attainment

	Sum of Square	Distribution frequency	Mean Square	Frequency	Sig.
AGE					
Between Groups	.005	1	.005	.008	.930
Within Groups	60.208	92	.654		
Total	60.213	93			
Parent's Average Monthly Income					
Between Groups	1.342	1	1.342	2.813	.097
Within Groups	43.892	92	.477		
Total	45.234	93			
Parent's Educational Attainment					
Between Groups	1.050	1	1.050	1.253	.266
Within Groups	76.198	91	.837		
Total	77.247	92			

Significant at .05 level

4. Is there a significant correlation among the sub-categories subsumed under challenges in learning Sciences among Senior High School STEM students of Sulu College of Technology Inc. as to teacher factors, subject matter, student ability, and parental support?

There is a moderate correlation among the sub-categories subsumed under the extent of the challenges encountered in learning Sciences among Senior High School STEM students of SCT Inc. in terms of teacher factors and subject matter. However, there is a low correlation in terms of student ability and parental support.

Conclusions

The following was concluded based on the findings of the study:

The majority of the respondents in terms of age are at the right age for their present grade level. Most of the Senior High School students are females, more than half of the parents earn below the minimum a month, and only a few are considered highly educated.

The disagreement of the respondents in terms of teacher factors, student ability, and parental support only proves that they do not contribute so much to the challenges encountered in learning Sciences while subject matter contributes fairly to the challenges encountered. The demographic profile of the respondents failed to show any differences in the extent of the challenges encountered in learning Sciences in terms of gender, parent's average monthly income, and parent's educational attainment proves that regardless of the aforementioned profiles, the respondents do not agree that they are contributory factors to the challenges encountered unlike age. It means the younger ones are challenged to a certain degree as compared to the older ones.

The moderate correlation in terms of teacher factors and subject matter goes to show that the variables are inseparable as far as teaching is concerned. Student ability and parental support however are not so much related to the challenges encountered in learning Sciences.

Recommendations

This study recommends the following:

1. Further study on the challenges encountered by students in learning Sciences should be conducted to make sure what affects them in learning the subject.
2. Future researchers on the same topic should add the variables like availability of laboratory facilities and the expertise of science teachers.
3. Science teachers should provide learners with activities that would challenge their imagination and curiosity about science.
4. Parents should support their children's education to lessen the challenges encountered by them in learning sciences.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers hereby attest that they have gained informed permission from the study respondents. Furthermore, the researchers guarantee the confidentiality of the data collected from participants. The research procedure was conducted with rigorous adherence to plagiarism guidelines, ensuring that the results were interpreted impartially and that their usage was limited to legitimate research.

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